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Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
OFLOXACIN AND SATRANIDAZOLE BY USING RP- HPLC****Vangalapudi Revathi^{1*}, Santanu Kumar Hotta², Chaitanya Bangari³,
Dr.M.B.Venkatapathi Raju⁴**¹Avanthi Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

A method was developed on trial & error basis by changing the variables wherever required. Finally a method was optimized and the conditions were determined. Method was developed by using RP HPLC Method During this optimization at every trial a new combination of mobile phase was tried to overcome the drawbacks of the previous run. Finally the method was optimized at trial 5, the optimized method was using 40 volumes of 20mM Phosphate buffer pH 3.0: 60 volumes of Acetonitrile at 305 nm and validated as per ICH guidelines.

The method was validated for system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, robustness, LOD and LOQ. The system suitability parameters were within limit, hence it was concluded that the system was suitable to perform the assay. The method shows linearity between the concentration range of 60-140µg / ml for Ofloxacin and 72-168 for Satranidazole. The % recovery of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole were found to be in the range of 98.0 % - 102.0 %. As there was no interference due to mobile phase, the method was found to be specific. The method was robust as observed from insignificant variation in the results of analysis by changes in Flow rate and wavelength variation separately and analysis being performed by different analysts.

Keywords: Acetonitrile, Ofloxacin, Satranidazole, Flow rate and wavelength**Corresponding author:****Vangalapudi Revathi,**

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INTRODUCTION:

A synthetic fluoroquinolone (fluoroquinolones) antibacterial agent that inhibits the supercoiling activity of bacterial DNA gyrase, halting DNA replication. Ofloxacin acts on DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, enzymes which, like human topoisomerase, prevents the excessive supercoiling of DNA during replication or transcription. By inhibiting their function, the drug thereby inhibits normal cell division. Satranidazole is an anthelmintic agent used for the treatment of accumulation of the pus in the liver caused by *Entamoeba histolytica* (amoebic liver abscess) and infections caused by protozoa in the stomach, intestines, or genital areas [1].

The concept of analytical chemistry lies in the precise and accurate measurements. On the literature survey it was found that Ofloxacin and

Satranidazole was estimated independently and in combination with other drugs by several chromatographic, spectrometric methods in pharmaceutical formulations and in biological samples.

In view of the need analytical method in the quality control laboratories for routine analysis of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole in formulations, the present work aims to develop simple and accurate instrumental methods for simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole and extend it for their determination in formulation and in laboratory prepared synthetic mixture[2].

Development and validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY:**Instruments used**

UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Nicolet evolution 100
UV-Visible Spectrophotometer software	Vision Pro
HPLC software	Spin chrome (LC SOLUTIONS)
HPLC	Shimadzu(LC 20 AT VP)
Ultra sonicator	Citizen, Digital Ultrasonic Cleaner
pH meter	Global digital
Electronic balance	Shimadzu
Syringe	Hamilton
HPLC Column	Inertsil ODS 3V(250x4.6mm) 5 μ m

Reagents used

Water	HPLC Grade
Sodium Acetate	AR Grade
Methanol	HPLC Grade
Potassium Phosphate	AR Grade
Acetonitrile	HPLC Grade
Ammonium acetate	AR Grade
Triethylamine	AR Grade

Ofloxacin and Satranidazole drugs	Gift Samples obtained from Chandra labs, Hyd.
Satromax O (200+300) (Ofloxacin-200 mg Satranidazole-300 mg) label claims). Mfg by: Orison Pharmaceuticals	Obtained from local pharmacy

FIXED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS [3]

Stationary Phase	Inertsil ODS, C18 Column, (250 x 4.6mm , 5 μ)
Mobile phase	Phosphate buffer+ACN(40:60) pH 3.0
Solvent ratio	40:60
Detection wavelength	305 nm
Flow rate	1.0 ml/ml
Operating Temperature	Room Temperature
Injection volume	20 μ l
Run time	6 min
Mode of operation	Isocratic elution

ASSAY [4-10]**Preparation of samples for Assay****Standard sample**

weigh accurately 50 mg of Ofloxacin and 60 mg of Satranidazole in 50 ml of volumetric flask and dissolve in 10ml of mobile phase and make up the volume with mobile phase. From above stock solution 100 μ g/ml of Ofloxacin and 120 μ g/ml of Satranidazole is prepared by diluting 1ml to 10ml with mobile phase. This solution is used for recording chromatogram.

Sample

10 Tablets (each Tablet contains 200 mg of Ofloxacin and 600 mg of Satranidazole) were weighed and taken into a mortar uniformly mixed. Test stock

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{DS} \times \frac{DT}{WT} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{AW}{LC} \times 100$$

Where,

AS: Average peak area due to standard preparation

AT: Peak area due to assay preparation

WS: Weight of Ofloxacin/ Satranidazole in mg

WT: Weight of sample in assay preparation

DT: Dilution of assay preparation

solutions of 100 μ g/ml of Ofloxacin and 120 μ g/ml of Satranidazole was prepared by dissolving weight equivalent to 200 mg of Ofloxacin and 600 mg of Satranidazole and dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5 min and dilute to 50ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 100 μ g/ml of Ofloxacin and 120 μ g/ml of Satranidazole was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.

Calculation:

The amount of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole present in the formulation by using the formula given below, and results shown in above table:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Chromatogram of Satranidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]	Height [%]	W05 [min]
1	2.133	1774.478	315.944	27.2	37.5	0.09
2	4.660	4739.581	527.300	72.8	62.5	0.14
	Total	6514.058	843.244	100.0	100.0	

Result for Satranidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

	Reten. Time	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Capacity [-]	Efficiency [th.pl]	Eff/l [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.133	0.090	1.381	0.00	3113	31127	-
2	4.660	0.140	1.222	0.00	6138	61380	12.928

Result for Satranidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase by assymetry

Observation:

The no of theoretical plates of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole were more than 2000. The tailing factor of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole was less than 2.0. Resolution between the peaks was more than 1.5. All the system suitability parameters were satisfied. Hence this method was optimised.

ASSAY

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-1

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-2

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-3

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-4

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-5

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-1

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-2

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-3

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-4

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-5

Results of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole

Ofloxacin		Satranidazole	
Standard Area	1	1721.236	4683.457
	2	1726.809	4664.742
	3	1773.368	4710.112
	4	1721.236	4683.457
	5	1757.262	4731.718
	Average	1740.471	Average 4694.697
Sample area	1	1774.478	4665.793
	2	1761.544	4680.906
	3	1780.429	4726.280
	4	1766.657	4717.394
	5	1775.269	4672.53
	Average	1771.675	Average 4692.581
Tablet average weight		924	mg 924
Standard weight		50	mg 150
Sample weight		231	mg 231
Label amount		200	mg 600
std.purity		99.6	99.7
Cal.:		202.77	mg 597.93
	% Assay	101.39	% 99.66

VALIDATION**Specificity:**

There is no interference of mobile phase, solvent and placebo with the analyte peak and also the peak purity of analyte peak which indicate that the method is specific for the analysis of analytes in their dosage form.

Blank chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-1

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-2

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-3

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-1

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-2

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-3

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole were calculated mathematically. The LOD of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole was found to be 5.78 μ g/mL and 2.98 μ g/mL. The LOQ of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole was found to be 17.53 μ g/mL and 9.03 μ g/mL respectively

Precision: Precision of method was demonstrated by

- Intraday precision
- Inter day precision

Ofloxacin		
S.No.	Rt	Area
1	2.130	1773.318
2	2.143	1757.981
3	2.147	1770.881
4	2.147	1774.701
5	2.120	1768.959
6	2.140	1753.751
Avg	2.1378	1766.599
Stdev	0.0108	8.649
%RSD	0.50	0.49

Method precision

Satranidazole		
S.No.	Rt	Area
1	4.787	4694.238
2	4.797	4671.269
3	4.803	4692.796
4	4.807	4714.121
5	4.697	4727.748
6	4.710	4733.29
Avg	4.767	4705.577
Stdev	0.050	23.671
%RSD	1.04	0.50

Method precision

Chromatogram of precision -1

Chromatogram of precision -2

Chromatogram of precision -3

Chromatogram of precision -4

Chromatogram of precision -5

Chromatogram of precision -6

Accuracy:

To study the reliability, suitability and accuracy of the method, recovery studies were carried out. To an equivalent quantity of formulation powder, a known quantity of standard Satranidazole and Ofloxacin were added to 80% and 120% level extracted with mobile phase and made up to mark with same. This solution was further diluted. The concentration of drugs present in resulting solution was determined using assay method and percentage recovery and

% RSD were calculated.

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-2

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-3

Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-2

:Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-3

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-2

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-3

Recovery Studies

Recovery	Ofloxacin					
	Amount taken mcg/ml	Area	Average area	Amount recovered	% recovery	Average recovery
80%	100	1765.789	1764.535	98.29	98.29	99.93%
	100	1779.064				
	100	1748.751				
100%	120	2142.357	2131.420	120.42	100.35	
	120	2122.300				
	120	2129.602				
120%	140	2465.152	2478.361	141.64	101.17	
	140	2504.779				
	140	2465.152				

Recovery	Satranidazole					
	Amount taken mcg/ml	Area	Average area	Amount recovered	% recovery	Average recovery
80%	120	4681.815	4690.851	120.66	100.55	100.02%
	120	4761.043				
	120	4629.696				
100%	144	5547.438	5553.105	144.06	100.04	
	144	5547.281				
	144	5564.596				
120%	168	6534.172	6527.407	167.12	99.47	
	168	6513.877				
	168	6534.172				

Linearity and Range

Satranidazole and Ofloxacin were found to be linear in the range of 60-140 μ g/mL for Ofloxacin and 72-168 μ g/mL for Satranidazole Calibration graphs were plotted using peak areas of standard drugs vs. concentration of standard solutions,

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-1

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-2

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-3

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-4

: Chromatogram of Linearity solution-5

Calibration data of Satranidazole and Ofloxacin by RP-HPLC

Sartanidazole	
Mcg	Area
72	2698.859
96	3732.111
120	4625.623
144	5624.484
168	6798.047

Ofloxacin	
mcg	Area
60	1029.758
80	1436.204
100	1769.976
120	2099.778
140	2502.128

Calibration graph of Satranidazole by RP-HPLC.

Calibration Graph of Ofloxacin by RP-HPLC

Robustness:

In order to demonstrate the robustness of the method, the following optimized conditions were slightly varied, ± 2 ml/min in flow rate, 3 ± 2 units in wavelength, The response factors for these changed chromatographic parameters were almost same as that of the fixed chromatographic parameters and hence developed method is said to be robust.

Robustness (change in flow)

Chromatogram of robustness variation in flow rate – 0.8 mL/min

Chromatogram of robustness variation in flow rate – 1.2 mL/min

Robustness (change in the wavelength)

Chromatogram of robustness variation in wavelength 303 nm

Chromatogram of robustness variation in in wavelength 307 nm

Results of Chromatogram of robustness variation in satranidazole and ofloxacin

Parameter	Satranidazole		Ofloxacin	
	Retention time(min)	Tailing factor	Retention time(min)	Tailing factor
Flow				
1.0ml/min	2.823	1.423	6.163	1.267
1.2ml/min	2.130	1.429	4.787	1.216
1.4ml/min	1.703	1.333	3.723	1.200
Wavelength				
306 nm	2.133	1.381	4.647	1.257
308nm	2.130	1.429	4.787	1.216
310nm	2.110	1.429	4.617	1.194

Ruggedness

The ruggedness of the method was studied by the determining the analyst to analyst variation by performing the Assay by two different analysts

Acceptance criteria:

The % Relative standard deviation of Assay values between two analysts should be not more than 2.0%.

Chromatogram of Analyst 01 standard preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 01 sample preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 02 standard preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 02 sample preparation

Results for Ruggedness

Ofloxacin	%Assay	Satranidazole	% Assay
Analyst 01	99.52	Analyst 01	99.31
Anaylst 02	98.39	Anaylst 02	96.05
%RSD(Rt)	1.00	%RSD(Rt)	1.07

Observation

From the observation the %RSD between two analysts Assay values not greater than 2.0%, hence the method was rugged.

FORCED DEGRADATION:

Thermal Degradation: Degradation was not observed when the sample solution was kept under heat at 105⁰ C for 24 hours

Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]
1	2.130	1756.234	310.882	27.13
2	4.787	4717.186	509.424	72.87
	Total	6473.420	820.306	100.00

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Efficiency [th.p]	Eff/l [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.130	0.090	1.381	3103	31030	-
2	4.787	0.143	1.216	6178	61785	13.399

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin by assymetry

ACID DEGRADATION: Degradation was not observed by the additon of 0.1 N HCl

Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]
1	2.133	1743.240	314.627	27.37
2	4.660	4626.820	524.291	72.63
	Total	6370.060	838.917	100.00

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Efficiency [th.pl]	Eff/ [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.133	0.087	1.381	3357	33568	-
2	4.660	0.140	1.194	6138	61380	13.119

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin by asymmetry

DEGRADATION BY UV: Degradation was not observed by exposure to UV light.

Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]
1	2.133	1777.567	318.678	27.47
2	4.647	4693.729	526.785	72.53
	Total	6471.296	845.462	100.00

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Efficiency [th.pl]	Eff/ [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.133	0.090	1.381	3113	31127	-
2	4.647	0.140	1.229	6103	61029	12.860

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin by asymmetry

ALKALINE DEGRADATION: Degradation was not observed by the additon of 0.1 N NaOH

Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]
1	2.140	1766.593	317.144	27.25
2	4.647	4717.429	531.852	72.75
	Total	6484.021	848.995	100.00

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Efficiency [th.pl]	Eff/l [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.140	0.090	1.450	3132	31322	-
2	4.647	0.137	1.194	6404	64042	13.015

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin by assymetry

PEROXIDE DEGRADATION (OXIDATION): Degradation was not observed when the sample was treated with 10% H₂O₂.

Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	Area [mV.s]	Height [mV]	Area [%]
1	2.140	1761.990	312.861	27.38
2	4.737	4672.155	517.569	72.62
	Total	6434.145	830.429	100.00

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin

	Reten. Time [min]	W05 [min]	Asymmetry [-]	Efficiency [th.pl]	Eff/l [t.p./m]	Resolution [-]
1	2.140	0.090	1.381	3132	31322	-
2	4.737	0.140	1.222	6342	63416	13.287

Results of Degradation of satranidazole and ofloxacin by asymmetry
No degradation was observed when sample was exposed to these conditions

CONCLUSIONS:

An attempt was made to develop a simple, accurate & precise stability indicating method for the simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole.

- A method was developed on trial & error basis by changing the variables wherever required. Finally a method was optimized and the conditions were determined. Method was developed by using RP HPLC Method During this optimization at every trial a new combination of mobile phase was tried to overcome the drawbacks of the previous run. Finally the method was optimized at trial 5, the optimized method was using 40 volumes of 20mM Phosphate buffer pH 3.0: 60 volumes of Acetonitrile at 305 nm and validated as per ICH guidelines.
- The method was validated for system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, robustness, LOD and LOQ. The system suitability parameters were within limit, hence it was concluded that the system was suitable to perform the assay. The method shows linearity between the concentration range of 60-140µg / ml for Ofloxacin and 72-168 for Satranidazole. The % recovery of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole were found to be in the range of 98.0 % - 102.0 %. As there was no interference due to mobile phase, the method was found to be specific. The method was robust as observed from insignificant variation in the results of analysis by changes in Flow rate and wavelength variation separately and analysis being performed by different analysts.
- The present method is validated and the results are better than previous methods which are performed on these drugs.
- Hence it can be concluded that the proposed method was a good approach for obtaining reliable results and found to be suitable for the routine analysis of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole in Tablets.
- Finally we propose the method is accurate, precise, linear, specific, and robust, stability indicating method for the simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole. So we recommend this method for the routine analysis of Ofloxacin and Satranidazole in tablets.

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